

Evaluation of anther culture-derived lines under upland conditions for the North Eastern Hill of India

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The low productivity of upland rice in the North Eastern Hill of India makes it an unprofitable crop; yet, it occupies about 20–25% of the cultivated rice area. Most local upland cultivars are long-duration, low-yielding, tall types that lodge at maturity. They are mostly susceptible to diseases such as blast and leaf scald. Because blast is a serious disease, a breeding program was started to develop blast-resistant upland rice lines with a yield potential of 4–4.5 t ha⁻¹ and that mature in 120–130 d. The higher production potential is expected to increase productivity, whereas the shorter duration will help increase cropping intensity. Anther culture shortens the breeding cycle because of rapid attainment of homozygosity, thereby shortening the period for developing new varieties. We report here the production and evaluation of doubled-haploid (DH) lines that outyielded all checks under rainfed upland conditions.

Nine DH lines were produced by anther culture of F₂ plants of a hybrid between PSN and 6131, following the

method of Gupta and Borthakur (1987). These lines were evaluated in replicated yield trials for 3 yr (1996–98) under the dry-seeded upland conditions of Barapani (950 m asl) in Meghalaya, India. All DH lines, improved checks, and the local check were sown in terraces in randomized complete blocks with five replications in 5.6-m² plots. Row-to-row and plant-to-plant distances were 20 cm and 10 cm, respectively. Data on various agronomic characters were recorded from five randomly selected plants from each replication. Unmilled rice yield, however, was calculated from the yield of 5.6-m² plots in each replication. Days to flowering were recorded when

more than 50% of the plants in a plot flowered. Data on disease reaction were recorded following the *IRRI standard evaluation system for rice*.

The average yield of RCPL 1-29 for 3 yr was the highest (4.4 t ha⁻¹), followed by RCPL 1-27 (4.2 t ha⁻¹) and RCPL 1-24 (4.0 t ha⁻¹). The highest yielding improved check (IET13459) yielded 3.1 t ha⁻¹ and the local check (Bali) yielded 2.6 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). All three DH lines had a compact and erect habit and intermediate maturity (123–127 d), and were semidwarf (109.9–111.8 cm) with high spikelet fertility (79.6–83.8%) (Table 2). They exhibited significantly higher yield per plant (7.9–9.2 g).

Table 1. Grain yield^a (t ha⁻¹) of doubled-haploid (DH) lines, improved checks, and local check, Barapani, Meghalaya, India, 1996–98.

Year	DH lines			Improved checks		Local check
	RCPL 1-29	RCPL 1-27	RCPL 1-24	IET13459	IET13783	Bali
1996	4.3 a	3.6 b	2.9 c	2.2 d	1.7 e	1.4 f
1997	3.5 a	3.3 b	3.3 c	3.2 d	2.3 f	2.9 e
1998	4.9 b	5.8 a	5.8 a	3.8 d	4.1 c	3.4 d
Av	4.4 a	4.2 ab	4.0 ab	3.1 cd	2.7 cd	2.6 d

^aValues in a row followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Comparison of some agronomic characters^a of doubled-haploid (DH) lines and checks evaluated at Barapani, Meghalaya, India, 1996–98.

Variety/line	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Fertile tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	Yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Hulling (%)	Milling (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	Blast reaction (under field conditions) ^b
<i>DH lines</i>												
RCPL 1-29	126	111.8	4.3	23.7	133.7	82	7.9	29.5	80	73	67	HR (0)
RCPL 1-27	123	111.5	4.0	22.8	129.7	80	9.2	40.4	83	76	69	HR (0)
RCPL 1-24	127	109.9	3.9	23.5	124.4	84	8.7	28.7	79	65	58	HR (0)
<i>Improved checks</i>												
IET13459	116	118.3	3.2	20.6	124.8	78	4.7	29.4	71	58	35	S (7)
IET13783	129	131.2	2.5	20.6	145.3	85	4.0	26.3	80	67	53	HR (0)
<i>Local check</i>												
Bali	129	131.2	2.5	20.6	145.3	85	4.0	26.3	82	67	59	S (8)

^aAv of 3 yr. ^bBased on a 0 (HR) to 9 (HS) scale; HR = highly resistant, HS = highly susceptible, S = susceptible.

Senescence of leaves, especially that of the flag leaf, was slower in the DH lines than in the checks. These lines had long bold grains with white kernel. RCPL 1-29, RCPL 1-27, and RCPL 1-24 were resistant to leaf blast under field conditions, whereas improved check IET13459 and Bali were both susceptible to blast (Table 2). In addition, Bali lodged at maturity, whereas IET13459 and IET13783 lodged only under high-fertility conditions. In contrast, the DH lines did not lodge even under high-fertility conditions. Hulling percentages of the DH lines were 83% in RCPL 1-27,

80% in RCPL 1-29, and 79% in RCPL 1-24 (Table 2). Milling percentages were 76% in RCPL 1-27, 73% in RCPL 1-29, and 65% in RCPL 1-24 (Table 2).

A multilocation trial was conducted on regional research farms during the 1998 wet season in five states (Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, and Nagaland) of the North Eastern Hill. The average unmilled yields of RCPL 1-29, RCPL 1-27, and RCPL 1-24 were 3.3, 2.5, and 3.1 t ha⁻¹, respectively. The yield performance of RCPL 1-29 in Manipur and Meghalaya did not show a significant

difference (4.7 t ha⁻¹ in Manipur and 4.9 t ha⁻¹ in Meghalaya). No blast incidence was recorded in the DH lines in any of the five states. Average yield improvement over local checks was 46% in Mizoram, 36% in Meghalaya, 28% in Arunachal Pradesh, 19% in Manipur, and 17% in Nagaland.

Reference

Gupta HS, Borthakur DN. 1987. Improved rate of callus induction from rice anther culture following microscopic staging of microspores in iron alum-haematoxylin. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 74:95-99.

Petei and Mocoi: two rice cultivars developed through anther culture in Argentina

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We developed two rice varieties, Petei and Mocoi, through anther culture. These varieties were released in 1997 for commercial cultivation in Argentina. Petei was developed from a cross involving cultivars Quella and Guayquiraro, which were made available to the rice program at the Julio Hirschhorm Experimental Station, FCAF. Selected plants from the F₂ population of this cross were used for anther culture at the biotechnology laboratory, FCA, UNNE. Mocoi was developed from crossing two F₁s (H342 and H161-28-2-2-1). H342's parents were Guayquiraro and Nucleoryza, whereas H161-28-2-2-1 had Calady 40 and IR1103-15-10 as parents. Anther culture was performed on the F₁s and progenies were multiplied for further evaluation.

Anther culture was used following the protocol given by Marassi et al (1993). Panicles from F₁ H353 and F₂ H319 at the booting stage containing pollen at the mid-uninucleate stage were pretreated (8 °C for 8 d). Anthers were plated on N6, a callus induction medium (Chu et al 1975) supplemented with 2 mg naphthalene acetic acid L⁻¹ and 0.5 mg kinetin L⁻¹, and

incubated in the dark at 27 ± 2 °C. Shoots were obtained on the regeneration medium. Flasks were transferred under light at 27 ± 2 °C. Plantlets were transferred to a rooting medium composed of MS (Murashige and Skoog 1962) culture solution that was free of hormones and supplemented with 8% sucrose. Plants were then transferred to the soil in the greenhouse until maturity, and the progeny was multiplied by the pedigree method. Data on callus formation and plant regeneration from anther culture of the two crosses are given in the table. The efficiency of anther culture (proportion of plants transferred to the soil

to total number of anthers cultured from the two crosses) was 8.4% for H319 and 5.4% for H353.

Petei is 90 cm tall, resists lodging, and has intermediate threshability. It matures in 115 d and its yield potential is 8.5 t ha⁻¹. Its grain is 5.9 mm long and 2.7 mm wide (short grain and special commercial type). The variety has 24.9% amylose, intermediate gelatinization temperature, 9.4% protein, and moderate resistance to blast. Because of its short growth duration, tolerance for low temperature, and good performance on saline soils, Petei is suited for growing in temperate climate under saline soil

Callus formation and plant regeneration from anther culture of rice.

Progeny	Anthers (no.)	Calli (%)	Calli with shoots (%)	Green shoots (%)	Plantlets transferred to soil (%)	Anther culture efficiency ^a (%)
H319 (F ₂)	8,900	14.6	75	85	90	8.4
H353 (F ₁)	8,100	11.0	70	80	87	5.4

$$^a \text{Anther culture efficiency} = \frac{\text{Number of plantlets transferred to soil}}{\text{Number of cultured anthers}} \times 100.$$